

A Study on Local Government Strategies in the 21st Century

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Abstract

In the twenty-first century, local face challenges related to service delivery, finance, workforce and citizen participation. Privatization was seen as an important innovation in the last decades of the twentieth century. The lack of cost savings and the loss of public values in market supply is another issue that needs to be evaluated. There are new approaches to privatization, increases in regulation and state enterprise. This draws attention to the differences between the old expression and the new experiences. The twenty-first century varies in terms of local' efforts to finance critical infrastructure. Attracting and retaining a skilled workforce encourages citizens to devise innovative solutions to public problems. It is clear that a focus on rebuilding capacities is imperative here. Innovations in public service delivery go beyond public-private partnerships. This brings accountability, equality and efficiency concerns to the forefront more effectively. It seems like a necessity to switch to balancing models. The idea of the Modernization of Local Government project consists in promoting a dialogue within the sector about the future. What has preoccupied Local Government leaders is that current reforms and ongoing calls for reform are more disconnected than ever before. What the industry needs should not be different from what communities need. Based on this, there is always a debate between councils about future Local Authorities. There remains an uncompromising interest in the past for reforms or initiatives that help keep progress. However, lack of consensus on what key reforms are or how to implement them does not support action. More work is required on a long-term and challenging project. Administrative councils, for local councils, may need some amendments to the Constitution as well, to be guaranteed (except in of excessive corruption or dysfunction), since they come to power by election. However, unlike other initiatives that will be discussed later, this should not be a high priority.

Keywords: *Local Governments, Local Government Strategies, Local Governments in the 21st Century, Local Government Strategies in the 21st Century*

1. Introduction

Some Local Government Strategists choose to maintain, refine and refine the models contained in the old Local Government Laws . Some insights are also required regarding the organizational structure of Local Government Strategists , which compels them to explore other models. Local Government Strategists have differing views on the idea of mutually accepted service and regulatory functions, requiring the following groups:

- a. *Those who believe that it is important to reach agreement between the three areas of government of all service and regulatory functions,*
- b. *Those who believe that some service and regulatory functions are carefully defined and accepted and other service functions are left optional,*
- c. *Those who believe that only regulatory functions are important,*
- d. *Those whose government dialogue is strong,*
- e. *Those who believe that all service functions will be activated as in the current Local Government Act, which is not mandated by mutual agreement.*

Although it is a challenging task, there are some aspects that are an important priority in the short and medium term. Local Government Strategists also cover issues that are urgent or require a high priority. General Local Government Strategists must strongly support the development of an alternative system for financing as well. Often, future involvement in providing funding or operational support is present throughout the strategies. However, there are other main topics and sub-items for Local Government Strategists who choose to pursue roles such as Fire Brigade and State Emergency Services. Local Government Strategists are divided on going further than what is currently being done and formally acting as conduits for community input in all local services related to whatever government area serves.

2. Controls Over Local Government Strategies

There are also relatively dangerous considerations that include criticism of services over which Local Government Strategists have no control. Supporters of this issue see it as a natural extension of their role of representing communities in other areas of government and as a natural part of Community Strategic Planning .

However, there are also the following comments

- i) requests by some communities to change local restrictions,
- ii) the demands of some communities to organize on a regional basis, and
- iii) metropolitan communities require many more Local Government Strategies and specialists (or even a single Local Government Strategies).

Local Government Strategists should pay attention to contemporary or emerging evidence supporting mergers based on economies of scale. The vast majority referred to studies that showed otherwise. Because the value of resource sharing and other joint strategies has been strongly promoted as an alternative. Still, there are suggestions that mergers are providing facilities and services for new Local Government Strategists now beyond the capacity of the old ones. ,

3. Economic Engines of the Global Economy

Cities are the economic engine of the global economy and are home to more than half of the global population. This makes them critical geographic areas where social, political and economic relations connect and develop. The mesh of systems that make up a city is dynamic and constantly transforming. Over the course of several decades, local political leaders and urban policy makers have developed various forms of 'strategic urban planning policies' that serve as the foundation for a city's growth path at the urban level, guiding medium- and long-term economic development and place-making. This is for specific purposes. Without designing and establishing a clear and overarching strategic direction for urban development, the complex systems that make up a city can become misaligned over time. Widening divisions and disruptions can be found among a city's human, economic, and ecological systems. Strategic urban planning is an essential tool within the administrative arsenal of local government to tap into the potential of urbanization to advance social and economic benefits through a coordinated framework. An entire local government typically develops these strategic urban planning policies with feedback and input from a wide range of public sector actors and key stakeholders from the private sector, community organizations and citizens.

Developing a comprehensive, clear and actionable strategic urban planning policy should remain a priority . Today, many studies on whether this is applied or not are found in the literature. These strategies require significant skills as they aim to structure the relationships

between a city's public and private sectors and wider civil society. Achieving this requires an urban government to be able to identify and reflect on the capacities of local actors. Thus, strategic urban planning policy can help generate symbiotic relationships between sectors and organizations. Because it is possible to create public value effectively in this way. While strategic city planning has the potential to be the foundation for advancing a city's long-term development goals, in practice it often falls short of the intended goal. Numerous challenges complicate designing strategic urban planning policies.

silos nature of local government organizations (Bai et al. 2016) and the tension between 'places' in the built environment and 'flows' of capital and resources (Castells 1996) are two critical challenges that cities commonly face when engaging in strategic urban activities. Planning processes ultimately reduce their effectiveness. Local governments - and public sector organizations in general - have become increasingly muted institutions over the past 40 years. Throughout this period, public institutions focused on developing private sector-like professional management structures and processes to maximize their ability to generate economic efficiency rather than create public value.

4. Different Approaches to Governance

There are different approaches to governance. Local government organizations are encouraged to design administrative structures characterized by segmented departments where sectorally divided expertise can undertake streamlined activities as individual nodes. However, this form of organization requires strong collaboration between departments to design holistic, systemic, flexible solutions rather than industry-specific policy. This is inappropriate for addressing broader societal and environmental challenges. Accordingly, this 40-year reshaping of the public sector has weakened local government's capacity to manage the relationship between physical development in the built environment and capital flows and social change in a coordinated direction towards equitable, inclusive and environmentally balanced outcomes.

Places within a city and the flows we mentioned above are made up of many public, private and civic actors. Coordinating these dispersed actors in a common direction requires a strong meeting body well connected to the range of organizations and with an understanding that the interests of each can be used to bring them to the famous table . This type of management

capability is not perceived to support short-term economic efficiency and has therefore been de-prioritized by many local governments. Also, due to the diminishing capabilities of local governments, the intended objectives in a city's strategic urban planning policy are often not achieved in the process of transforming urban policy into administrative operational practices.

Actions get stuck in ineffective bureaucratic planning processes. Large-scale initiatives are not designed to include the complexity of urban practices. This weakness, which hinders urban transformation, hinders large-scale infrastructure projects. This can be exemplified by resource-intensive programs that fail to deliver the intended benefit and instead create a high cost on a city's balance sheet.

The increasingly limited capacity of local governments is the subject of agile and iterative work that enables 'failure to learn quickly'. Risk taking and actions are gradually changing. Building the ability to scale is also becoming more critical than ever. From housing affordability to flexible mobility systems and climate adaptation, these changes have continued. To address the critical urban challenges of the 21st century, local governments face other challenges as well. It is necessary to shape their economic development towards social goals. For this, he should develop the necessary dynamic abilities. Institutional shortcomings that traditionally hinder strategic urban planning have to be overcome. Experts and citizens alike agree that the application of information technology (IT) to the challenges of public administration and effective service delivery is one of the most powerful and transformative governance trends in the developing world. Such “e-governance” or “digital governance” applications began with the computerization of intra-governmental management systems for finance, payroll and other key government functions.

Subsequently, there has been a proliferation of information sharing with citizens through web pages and other basic means of access. Most initially there was only one-way communication from the government to the broader public. The possibilities of technology can accelerate and change the flow direction. In the late 1990s IT (Computer Technology) benefited in streamlining business processes. It has been used to restructure and create "one-stop shops" to facilitate better service delivery. Websites have become more capable and adaptable, serving as two-way channels through which government business can be run. Around this time, international organizations such as the Organization for Economic Co-operation and

Development (OECD), the European Union and the United Nations began to monitor the use of such technologies. Political leaders from around the world have begun to deploy their IT initiatives on their own. Significant resources have been invested in the development and implementation of e-governance strategies. Seeing national agendas as an important priority is also an issue that needs to be evaluated. More recently, the rapid expansion of mobile technologies and mobile phone use, which exceeds 70 percent of the population in some countries, offers a host of new opportunities to access services and monitor government performance. In bureaucratic terms, this revolution has emerged with breathtaking speed (World Bank 2015).

In two decades, such systems (including financial management, customs, taxation, e-procurement, payroll and human resource management) have expanded from a small handful of countries to more than 120 countries. In contrast, the first ombudsman institution emerged in Sweden in 1810. However, it has been 120 years since the next office was created. By 1970, less than a dozen countries had established such institutions. Various dynamics have driven this rapid growth.

The relentless and well-documented qualitative expansion of computer technology has reduced the relative costs of such systems. It has greatly expanded its capabilities compared to the past. Governments have quickly discovered that such technologies can be useful in solving a range of problems, from document processing to coordinating complex workflows that cross corporate boundaries. Under a well-functioning e-governance regime, information and records on the internal functioning of governments and policies will be available. Thus, transparency and accountability can be promoted (Brown and Garson 2013; Lee 2010; Song and Cho 2007). In addition, e-governance creates an innovative environment that enhances the efficient delivery and effectiveness of public goods and services (Chen and Dimitrova 2008; Millard 2008). For example, the application of IT to the government procurement process can streamline its management and reduce associated costs, as well as create a more transparent and fairer payment system.

5. Modernization Process

Faced with these dual views of the modernization process, particularly global trends at the local government level, we have at least four studies at the beginning of 1997 on a broadly similar trend. The WZB Study, conducted between 1995 and 1997, significantly broadened and deepened the set of criteria. Applied to the example of a larger pioneer city . In recent years, researchers have applied a relatively consistent set of criteria over a medium-term period – five years.

It is rare to experience such an accumulated database in empirical social scientific research. To this extent, the findings can be seen as relatively robust and generalizable. This does not mean that it is impossible to imagine events that could lead to a situation where several hierarchically organized forces make and implement decisions that shape future society-wide outcomes. Still, there seems to be a consensus that the long-term trend is towards a broader, much less hierarchical distribution of capacity for effective action. Changes in this general direction appear to have a good chance of being viable in the long run as long as the continued expansion and deepening of democracy, perfectly competitive open markets and the rule of law continues. As a result, losers from change often make every effort to preserve the governance and authority structures of the past, while winners feel that the institutions and compensation arrangements of the past should no longer apply. Transition periods often lead to radical differences in the perception of risk, or more precisely, in the extent of people's feelings of insecurity.

Typically, those who do not actively create new rules and power structures tend to perceive major changes as driven by the uncontrollable operation of external and dangerous forces. Fear in public and private spaces becomes a major obstacle to change and the emergence of truly innovative forms of management suited to the new conditions. Indeed, the beginning of the 21st century seems fraught with many of these transitional conflicts and fears.

Confidence in established forms of government that cannot claim the effectiveness or legitimacy needed to move society towards its goals is waning. At first glance, the inadequacies of existing forms of governance seem to add to the major challenges likely to be posed by the technological, economic and social changes that may occur in the coming decades. Indeed, this risk appears significant and the potential for damage is serious.

As a result of the social, economic and environmental changes typical of the 21st century, many Western democratic countries have implemented local government reforms, including legal,

socioeconomic, administrative, political and spatial reforms (Ebinger et al., 2019; Kuhlmann & Bouckaert , 2016).).

Garcea and Lesage (2005) defined local structural reform as the restructuring of local government in terms of the number, type and size of municipalities, semi-municipalities and municipal special-purpose units . Local government reforms are also referred to as multi-level governance. It includes broad-based initiatives to coordinate decision-making and public policy in the face of overlapping and judicial fragmentation of authority in large metropolitan areas and urban areas (Enderlein et al., 2010; Storper , 2014). Multilevel governance can be defined as the horizontal and vertical interdependence of intertwined government networks at various regional layers and levels, such as supranational , national, regional and local (Marks, 1993).

Multilevel governance literature agrees that spreading governance across multiple players is more likely to solve problems and is more efficient, specialized and professional than a single player (Hooghe & Marks, 2004; Peters & Pierre, 2004). However, one of the criticisms of multi-level governance is that it undermines democracy as it deprives citizens of their representation and makes governing bodies less accountable to the people (Bache et al., 2016). It also provides a clearer view of what the public wants and is willing to accept, even though public opinion, social voice and public choice in metropolitan governance may be 'scattered' (Storper , 2014). However, there is a serious lack of systematic empirical research on multilevel governance, its possible consequences on governance and democracy (Paadopoulos , 2005), and the possible impact of public choice on this relationship (Storper , 2014).

To fill this gap, it is necessary to explore the effects of multi-level governance practices, namely three specific and competing structural reforms – consolidation, unbundling and clustering of local government authorities – on residents' assessments of local governance and democracy. These reforms have cross-cutting goals such as maintaining a balance between decentralization and centralization, solving problems involving economies of scale, increasing economic and administrative efficiency, improving performance and efficiency in the delivery of local services, and narrowing the gaps between groups (Blatter , 2006). However, the most important difference between the three structural reforms is the initiator of the reform. Mergers are often mandated by the central government on a top-down approach.

Unbundling is the result of pressure from multiple local stakeholders. Therefore, they represent an ad hoc, bottom-up coordination, which is usually centralized and top-down, aimed at reversing the decision-making process that results in consolidation. Finally, unlike mergers and unbundling, local government clustering is based on the concepts of volunteering and cooperation. It is a bottom-up strategy initiated by locally elected leadership (Ebinger et al., 2019; Zeedan, 2017). Despite the widespread use of various structural reforms, there is no consensus among researchers and policy designers on the necessity, positive impact and cost of these reforms (Bel & Warner, 2015; Houwelingen, 2017; Migali et al., 2017; Strebel, 2019), efficiency and leads to a fundamental dichotomy between democracy (Reingewertz & Serritzlew, 2019). Moreover, empirical studies examining the consequences of local structural reforms mainly focus on financial aspects (eg, Migali et al., 2017). Thus, this article is a response to the call to expand existing theoretical knowledge and examine the effects of local structural reforms on local governance and democracy (Drew et al., 2019; Ebinger et al., 2019; Martin, 2015; Reingewertz & Serritzlew, 2019). Shedding light on this research question is of theoretical and practical importance. From a theoretical perspective, this study can contribute to the field by examining competing municipal reforms, taking into account the tensions between centralization and decentralization, regionalism and separatism, localism and new localism. From a practical standpoint, our findings can help politicians, policy designers, programmers, geographers, sociologists and administrators at all levels of government reduce the cost of implementing such reforms and provide clues to the changes in public opinion that can be expected from these changes.

6. Competition over Land Ownership

Consistent with the initial assumptions that every point in space is different from every other point in space and that inequality will forever be the result of asymmetrical power relations, it is natural to expect that the competition over land ownership is not over yet (Gyuris, 2016). In a recent study, Beeri et al. (2020) conceptualized the concept of regionalism in local and central-local areas. While territoriality refers to the political organization of space that connects land and borders (Shah, 2012), central-local territoriality is defined as the spatial, political relations between local governments, communities, classes, and ethnic groups, and between these groups and communities (Beeri et al., 2020). In other words, it is necessary to take a

structural approach to understanding the balance of power in space and its impact on land and borders. By transferring control of land and related resources to a local authority and thus to a community, the central government has actually taken political action, using its power in favor of certain communities (Marsh et al., 2010). Such an action may benefit a local leader, but deprive a neighboring local community of these benefits. As such, structural local reforms are more likely than not to have political consequences on local governance, local democracy, and therefore public opinion (Krippendorff , 2005). Since the end of the 20th century, the erosion of the nation's power to govern top-down and shape public policy has led to the development of bottom-up approaches based on the power of civil society and local authorities. At a further stage, approaches have emerged that combine top-down and bottom-up approaches. As a result, advocates of local government have sought to retain local sovereignty in the hands of local representatives to advance local democracy even at the expense of a lower standard of living (Sørensen & Torfing , 2009).

Another perspective that developed simultaneously was that the region was seen as a spatial unit whose boundaries were formed by the ongoing social structure. A functional region is a natural result of local social interactions and economic conditions (Jonas , 2012; Paasi , 2003). Policy makers tend to agree that larger regional structures should include more players and be given more autonomy (Reingewertz & Serritzlew , 2019). However, recent trends such as multilevel governance and new regionalism are flawed solutions (Storper , 2014). The new regionalism, the most advanced form of multi-level governance today, sees the region as an ecosystem that integrates economic, planning, political, social and cultural aspects to ensure efficient, inclusive and sustainable economic development (Blatter , 2006; Deas & Ward , 2000). Both multilevel governance and new regionalism introduce complexities that will likely result in new challenges. They reflect a conflict between ideologies (Peters & Pierre, 2004), between local and general traditions (Mill , 1861), democracy and efficiency (Kersting & Vetter , 2003), shared responsibility and delegation of authority (Paadopoulos , 2005).

Local structural reforms involve local governance and local democracy, with the relationship between local governance and local democracy. Structural reforms are a comprehensive form of regulation that have the potential to affect administrative performance and create changes in the perspectives of local governments (Ebinger et al., 2019).

Among the many possible effects, it would be right to choose to focus on four topics:

“residents' perceptions of local manageability and public participation in decision-making processes, their satisfaction with local services and their trust in local government”

Local manageability has been studied especially in political sciences since the 1990s. Local manageability has different, overlapping definitions and uses that refer to the form of government, political culture, management perspectives, and interrelationships among participants in government operations (Kooiman et al., 2008; Osborne et al., 2013). Local manageability can be defined as the ability to govern and the extent of the government's political and professional capacity to make and implement decisions. In other words, this term refers to the ability of the local government to use its legitimate authority to implement policy. Public participation in decision-making processes has been studied from various perspectives, among them governance and politics (Vigoda-Gadot & Cohen , 2004). Arnstein (1969) argued that popular participation involves the redistribution, transfer or decentralization of authority and power. Doing so allows the public to take and make decisions on public issues ranging from technical information to partnerships through consultation. Public participation has a number of complementary purposes, including promoting public honesty and fairness, improving decision-making, and building trust. Satisfaction with local services is an important indicator of residents' evaluations as they experience the municipality's products and services. This is a key performance measure of public institutions (Van Ryzin , 2004). A number of theories have examined the factors affecting satisfaction with local services. For example, expectancy theory claims that assistants make rational comparisons between performance and a certain standard (Beeri et al., 2018).

Theories in the field of political science suggest that satisfaction is a derivative of the response of politicians and bureaucrats to the demands of residents, which requires a kind of secret social contract based on justice. Public choice theory emphasizes the combination of service quality and the extent to which the public can choose that service (Vigoda , 2000).

However, the basic principles of the approach appear broadly applicable and are being translated and tested at local and local decision-making levels. This policy brief outlines five key areas for research and policy to explore mission-driven innovation at the urban scale, based on emerging analysis from leading cities and local governments that have adopted the approach. By exploring and assessing these critical areas, local government organizations can drive

mission-driven innovation within certain policy constraints. they will be better equipped to make them operational and to deal with the challenges that affect their strategic planning processes.

7. Basic Research and Policy Agendas

Each city has unique geographic, cultural, economic and political characteristics that make it difficult to generalize best practices, requiring context-specific nuance and location-based knowledge and awareness. While from our early experience with mission-driven innovation the approach appears to have wide relevance among cities with diverse characteristics, at least five areas must be explored by research and policy to ensure robust use of the framework at the city level. It is widely recognized that existing urban finance flows create increasing financial barriers to the delivery of essential services, far from achieving the more systemic investments needed, for example, to decarbonize transport systems or meet the demand for affordable housing. In many countries, local government finance is highly centralized, with strict legal structures dictating financial decision-making, limiting the potential for autonomous revenue generation for local-level administrations. The mandates position local government organizations as market-shaping institutions, encouraging cities to navigate this complex and restrictive local government financing system. However, in many contexts, the political economy is such that tax powers are highly centralized at the national level, forcing local governments to explore fiscal devolution opportunities or to modify macroeconomic financial flows through advanced multi-level governance structures that can enable urban regeneration (King 1989).). Missions should be used to help cities redesign the short-term annual budgeting process that statically balances revenue with loss, and instead create a long-term asset-based investment mindset. To this end, further research is needed to explore how a local government mission can create city-led financial instruments for holistic change at the city level.

innovation as a framework to overcome this barrier requires a local government organization to develop new corporate designs with key capabilities, specific organizational cultures, practices and processes. There are a number of questions surrounding how these organizational and institutional silos can be resolved in practice to enable mission-driven innovation to fully

catalyze the transformation of a local government agency into the type of 'dynamic bureaucracy' that can holistically address cross-departmental-based policy challenges . There are three areas that practitioners and researchers alike can explore to examine how local government organizations can use mission-driven innovation to break down their institutional silos:

- a. ***Institutional design: Local governments traditionally*** organize their technical expertise into specialized departments that operate effectively independently of each other . This Local government borrowing is one way cities can make long-term investments in infrastructure ranging from waste treatment plants to renewable energy generation capacity, flood defense systems and even education systems. For example, San Francisco, California (San Francisco Public Utilities Commission 2020) and Asheville , North Carolina (McDaniel 2015) are among the growing numbers of cities in the United States and beyond that have successfully used green bonds to finance sustainability-related infrastructure.
- b. ***E-governance*** also improves public disclosure of information on expenditures and policy-making processes, thereby increasing government credibility and reducing the possibility of corruption. From a business perspective, companies can invest their resources more efficiently as they can spend less time and energy visiting government offices in search of information. Moreover, e-governance tends to promote fairness by making information equally accessible to all, provided that the problem of the digital divide is addressed. E-governance embodies equality by demonstrating its belief that all members of the public benefiting from government services should be able to receive administrative information without discrimination and have equal opportunities to be involved in the policy-making process. Therefore, its practice is perceived as more “value neutral” and is embraced by countries based on both authoritarian and democratic traditions. Whether it is actually value neutral has been the subject of extensive and ongoing debate.
- c. ***Not all IT practices*** have been equally transformative. Current research has shown that such solutions are typically most effective when applied to routine,

predictable, and easily monitored tasks and processes. Complex tasks or tasks involving a large amount of discretion typically do not see comparable benefits. The dissemination of information and the use of online services tend to be directed towards the youth, the educated, the urbanites, and those who are better off financially. While social media is a powerful tool to draw attention to blatant and dire government failures, such as incidents of corruption or police abuse, it is less effective at identifying ongoing dysfunction in areas characterized by complex causal chains and chronically poor performance. Even more sobering, many automation efforts in the public sector fail. An analysis of IT projects in developing countries suggested that about 30 percent of them were complete failures ; 50-60 percent are partial failures with significant budget and timeouts; and less than 20 percent meet their targets in terms of time, cost and functionality (World Bank 2016).

- d. **World Bank-sponsored IT projects** were rated as “failed” as opposed to the average of 18 percent for all Bank projects. Even in OECD countries, government failure rates are significant. A survey of IT projects in the United States reported success rates of 59 percent in retail, 27 percent in manufacturing, and only 18 percent in government (The standish Group International 2001). Korea's journey from a devastated and war-ravaged country in the 1950s to a developing country in the 1960s to an advanced information society in the 21st century is remarkable by any measure.

In the context of the international debate, a particularly important point to stress here is that administrative reform is much more than mere internal modernization: administrative reform aims, above and beyond internal modernization, to change the interfaces between government and the market. However, among the three megatrends, internal modernization of administration has played a dominant role in terms of local government modernization from the very beginning, but it is a trend that is sustained and even intensified. It is no coincidence to find trends involving an increasingly market-oriented approach of local government, at a much lower level but at a very rapid rate of growth. Democratization and devolution measures, on the other hand, are relatively few in number and exhibit weak growth rates. In the United States, it is a historical fact that democratic innovations in democratic governance must be reconciled

with our Madison tradition to be legitimate, however effective they may promise to be. Power in the Madisonian scheme is carefully divided between rival branches and levels of government. Negotiation—option-altering reflection in the service of the public interest—is the domain of a senatorial elite buffered from the immediacy of everyday concerns.

8. Competition Between Arms And Levels Of Government

Competition between branches and levels of government maintains freedom by providing checks and counterweights against the excessive ambitions of any part of the government machinery. By blurring the division of labor between branches and levels of government and linking the ultimate solution of major policy problems to everyday collaborative problem-solving, empiricism rejects this Madisonian legacy and perhaps puts our freedoms at risk. The empirical accountability established by problem-defining legislation and broad problem-solving powers to local organizations can nevertheless be regarded as a neo-Madisonian generalization of the original design for three reasons (Dorf and Sabel , 1998; Sabel , Fung , and Karkkainen , 2000, pp. 109-112).

Like old federalism, neo-Madisonism underpins a flexible mutual accountability between center and locality, impartial expert and concerned citizen. However, it makes the division of labor between regional units the temporary and correctable result of their work, not the expression of historically established responsibilities. In other words, neo-Madisonism simultaneously denaturalizes our framework of government—because the boundaries of mutually accountable, problem-solving units are no longer considered given—while linking it more directly to the surprising possibilities of citizens' lives—because problem-solving units try to uncover these surprises. It is shaped and reshaped by practical negotiation towards meaning and meaning. In retrospect, the success of the welfare state has been seen as dependent on the shared ethos or ethical identity of its citizens:

“Only if citizens recognize each other as basically the same, they will agree to redistribute resources in favor of those who fall short in market exchanges.”

As heterogeneous peoples are forced to unite in unified forms of government under the pressure of globalization, the common basis of redistributive solidarity is jeopardized. “How can experimentation contribute to the re-establishment of solidarity under conditions of radical

diversity? (Scharpf , 1999). Trust in local authority plays an important and central role in many disciplines, including psychology, sociology, education, economics and political science (Beeri et al., 2018). They are united in the common denominator of building trust based on people's subjective experiences, perspectives, and social experience of emotions, cognitions, and behaviors. Unified local governments, governance and democracy Structural reform, in the form of unification of local governments, changes the map of local government. Usually enforced by the central government, this reform (though it may be voluntary) unites two or more local authorities in a new political and economic organizational unity. Hence, it is a structure imposed on residents from top to bottom (Reingewertz , 2012). In a sense, unification of local governments is a New Public Management practice under the auspices of which local governments borrow organizational principles from the business sector (Reingewertz & Serritzlew , 2019). Accordingly, unification of local governments is a government tool designed to promote economies of scale. The aim is to streamline administration, improve governance and provide better municipal services. However, opinions on the effectiveness of combining government officials are mixed (eg Boyne , 1995; Hansen , 2015; Martin, 2015). Some researchers have cited empirical observations that support the efficiency and economic savings involved in such mergers (Migali et al., 2017; Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), 2014; Reingewertz , 2012). Under certain conditions, such as the region's situation, particularly its size, number of municipalities, and past reforms, mergers may trigger further investment and professionalisation (Ebinger et al., 2019). In contrast, other scholars have found no economic advantage in terms of size, arguing that mergers do not result in cost savings for services. In fact, they may even impair their effectiveness as information asymmetries increase and preferences become more heterogeneous (Bel & Warner, 2015; Hanes , 2015; Oates , 1972; Soukopova et al., 2014). Therefore, opinions are divided from the narrow economic cash flow perspective. However, another, no less important question is whether mergers harm or help manageability and democracy. Here again the evidence is mixed. Opponents of the merger strongly believe that it has negative consequences and an unpredictable future (Drew et al., 2019). On the one hand, government agencies with larger budgets are likely to have higher salary levels that enable them to hire more qualified managers. Doing so can have a significant positive impact on local government performance and decision-making. It can also encourage public participation in the decision-making process (Ebinger & Bogumil , 2016; Reingewertz , 2012). On the other hand, the central government may choose

to unify as a way of increasing its political power and thus weakening the power of different, homogeneous, united and self-governing local communities. Using such a format, the central government can micromanage them and limit their powers and budgets (Strebels , 2019). Thus, unification of local governments, even if planned and done explicitly, is liable to erode and limit their ability to make policy, increase their dependence on the central government, and undermine local democracy (Oates , 1972).

The erosion of local democracy stems from the basic logic that voters may feel less dependent on their representatives in larger municipalities due to the quantitative reduction in representation. From here, it is easy for residents to feel that the merger undermines their autonomy and local manageability (Lassen & Serritzlew , 2011; Zeedan , 2017). Also, residents may feel they have less access to elected officials and less opportunity to participate in local decisions. However, there are comparative studies of municipalities by Houwelingen (2017) and Ebinger et al. (2019), concluding that it is rather difficult to determine that the size of the municipality affects the degree of political participation. They also noted that the effects are complex, contradictory and therefore require further research. It is important to understand that unifying state authorities is not just a technical combination of administrations, budgets and assets.

Indeed, such a merger could potentially undermine the fabric of social life and the self-identification and identity of each of the communities that existed before the merger. Therefore, residents may have strong objections to mergers that undermine their trust in local government (Fitjar , 2019). While trust in local government takes a long time to build up, it is quite easy to harm local government, especially when active measures are not taken to nurture that trust. As a result, satisfaction with local services, which is a derivative of trust in local leadership (Beeri et al., 2018), tends to deteriorate as a result of a merger. Studies have reported a negative relationship between the size of the local government and the satisfaction of residents with the quality of service provided (Soukopova et al., 2014).

9. Conclusion

Consequently, failure to consider these factors, coupled with incompatibilities between different communities, has led to the abandonment of this type of reform (Beeri , 2020;

Committee for the Promotion of Regionalism in Israel , 2019). At the same time, alternative initiatives for the arrangement of the local government map have begun to emerge. In the 2000s, coalitions began to form between local governments and third sector private organizations and NGOs. In addition, temporary agreements for functional cooperation between local governments have proliferated, as do co-industrial zones, which require income distribution among a number of neighboring local governments to improve regional economic development. However, the most important step in implementing the concept of regionalism , albeit slowly and limitedly , involved encouraging local governments to voluntarily adopt and operate under the auspices of regional clusters (Beerli , 2020). Perceived local manageability reflects residents' perceptions of local government's ability to design and implement local policy (Kooiman et al., 2008). Based on the experience in the sample cities, as noted above, the most important conditions for initiating reconstruction processes are listed . The critical question at the current stage of the restructuring process therefore goes beyond initiation and concerns the sustainability of such reform developments. History is littered with examples of large-scale reform projects that, after a short period of time, stagnate or even fail completely. Based on the (so far) successful administrative modernization processes in the sample cities, it is possible to temporarily identify some promising approaches to "institutional evolution" as a means of stabilizing the actions of the actors involved:

- *Framework of conditions set by the central government*
- *such an institutional framework can only provide a framework that balances local restructuring programmes;*
- *New actor networks, rules and practices, and the creation of competitive markets between public and private suppliers have been determined to the extent that institutions created in the most developed cities are no longer subject to detrimental and opportunistic influences by individual actors;*
- *The trend towards expanding representative and participatory response mechanisms in the political sphere has created an incentive structure for citizen-centred policy and governance that would be very difficult to dismantle;*

- Malone 1997), which creates a significant resource potential in managers who can no longer be used in the traditional hierarchical administrative style (Roughshod).

A polycentric institutional evolution of this type may focus on a continuous development path of local government modernization over time and thus overcome the historical arbitrariness of the decisions of certain actors and the "transitional" characteristics of many reform projects. In summary, the transition from the initial stage to the institutionalization stage is perhaps the main challenge in establishing sustainable local government modernization. Multicentre institutional evolution can constitute the decisive direction and critical precondition for such sustainability.

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